

TOPIC- IDEOGRAPHIC CLASSIFICATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE COMPARED LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article considers phraseological units from the point of view of cultural linguistics. It is noted that the phraseological composition of any language is the most specific part of the culture of the nation, as it reflects lifestyles, behaviors, traditions and customs, stereotypes and symbols of the people. The main features of the phraseological units are described with cultural identity. Attention is paid to the internal form of phraseological unit as the primary interpretation of reality and the subsequent fixation of the image in the language. Some specific examples are given to define that the study of phraseological units of a particular culture contributes to a better understanding of the way of life of the country.

Keywords: phraseological unit, cultural linguistics, integrity of meaning, inner form, cultural characteristics of ethnic groups.

In recent years, the question of ideographic classification of the phraseological fund of various languages has been increasingly raised.

The study of phraseological units by thematic-ideographic groups, i.e. from the point of view of the concepts they denote, is important for the following reasons:

1) in different languages, phraseological units are "generated" by similar life situations and phenomena, therefore, the ideographic classification of phraseological units helps to solve the question of the nature and essence of

phraseological units; 2) in the ideographic classification of phraseological units, synonymic and antonymic relations are revealed between them, and, consequently, systemic connections in the phraseological fund of the language are revealed; 3) the experience gained by linguists in the ideographic distribution of the phraseological corpus of any language is extremely important when creating ideographic dictionaries, because such dictionaries are of great practical value for writers, poets, translators.

A comparative study of thematic and ideographic groups of phraseological units of two or more languages makes it possible to identify not only national specifics, but also typologically common in psychology, everyday life, history, culture, which goes back to the genetic kinship of certain peoples.

The phraseological units of the compared languages vividly convey the worldview of each nation, based on the actualization of certain fragments of objective reality due to a number of extralinguistic reasons, the most important of which are, in our opinion, the way of life of the people, the peculiarities of its cultural and historical development, national psychology, reflecting the ways of spiritual experience of the world.

The outstanding Russian scientist of the XIX century I.I. Sreznevsky paid great attention to the close connection of the language with the culture of its people. He noted that "the people express themselves more fully and more faithfully in their language. The people and the language cannot be represented without each other. The people act, their activity is controlled by the mind, the mind and activity of the people are reflected in their language."

This problem has acquired particular importance in our time in connection with the broad development of international relations, in connection with the problem of communication of people belonging to different cultures. Interlanguage contacts require that the language be studied in parallel with the study of the national and cultural specifics of the native-speaking people. "Reality is presented

differently in different languages, each new foreign word makes us think about what lies behind it and the corresponding Russian word." Of particular interest are studies on the material of foreign languages. The most widely presented works on the material of the English language by D.O. Dobrovolsky, O.A. Dmitrieva, V.M. Svitsky, G.S. Klychkov, etc. In the field of the Russian language, this issue is covered in the works of D.S. Likhachev, Yu.S. Stepanov, N.M. Babkin, G.F. Balykova, Yu.A. Gvozdarev, V.M. Mokienko, etc. In these works, it is convincingly shown that a significant part of phraseological units arise on a national-cultural basis specific to each country. The structure and meaning of such units have a deeply national specificity, which is determined by the conditions of material and spiritual,

cultural, socio-economic life of the native-speaking people, its history, social structure, customs and way of thinking.

A certain contribution to the development of this aspect of phraseology was made by scientists V.S. Vinogradov, N.N. Kurchatkina, A.V. Suprun, E.I. Levintova, E.M. Wolf, E.A. Maltseva, etc., explaining the motivation of phraseological units, convincingly illustrates that the origin of most phraseological units is closely related to the life of the people and its history.

The sources of phraseological units are the most diverse spheres of activity of the native-speaking people. Let's highlight the main, most productive sources.

Production activity of people. Phraseological units related to the material sphere of society belong to this group. As examples, we can cite mainly those phraseological units that have been completely reinterpreted and over time have lost all connection with the image that formed the basis of a stable phrase. Russian: to let off steam; to pull the rig; clumsy work; to sharpen the straps (to sharpen the straps - chiseled posts for railings, having fun talking); to pull the strap (from the speech of boatmen pulling barges against the current of the river, harnessed to the straps); green street (from the speech of railway workers); he

took up the wheelbarrow, do not say that he is not a dozen (from the old practice of earthworks, when a worker who carried the earth on a wheelbarrow, tied the wheelbarrow to the handles of the wheelbarrow to facilitate his work and threw it over his shoulders, taking up this work, people should not have complained of ill health and weakness); in English: putsnib in the cart - (lit.: put someone-L. in the cart) put in a difficult position, willing horse - (lit.: diligent horse) hard worker; go round like a horse in a mill - all the time to go along the beaten path; lay the first stone - (lit.: lay the first stone) to start something.

The analysis of the spheres of human activity that supply rich lexical material from which phraseological units of the Russian and English languages are created in comparison allows us to draw certain conclusions about the peculiarities of the language and culture of the native-speaking peoples:

1. Phraseological units reflecting the activities of peasants, fishermen, hunters, sailors, craftsmen, representatives of various industries: in Russian; *сапожник без сапог, тянуть ляжку, прибрать вожжи к рукам*; in English: *work one's head off - работать не покладая рук, take horse - ехать верхом, hard labor- каторжные работы, forced labor-принудительный труд*.

2. Phraseological units reflecting the activities of cultural representatives (artists, artists, musicians, etc.): in Russian: *под занавес, горе от ума, свежо предание, а верится с трудом, поэтическая жилка, зарыть талант в землю, гвоздь программы*; in English ; *play second fiddle -играть вторую скрипку, in tune- настроенный (о музыкальном инструменте), sing in tune- петь на лад, call the tune -задавать тон, the tune the old cow died of - режущий слух мотив, плохо исполняемая музыка, carry across the footlights - иметь успех, понравиться публике (о пьесе, спектакле)*.

3. Phraseological units reflecting the activities of various strata of the intelligentsia (doctors, lawyers, teachers, etc.): in Russian: *закон не писан для кл., что доктор прописал*; in English; *call of duty- долг службы, on call- по*

вызову/ по требованию.

4. Phraseological units reflecting various sports, games, entertainment; in Russian: *спутать карты, положить на обе лопатки*; в английском языке: *come up to the scratch— 1) (спорт.) подойти к стартовой черте; 2) быть готовым к борьбе, быть в форме, действовать решительно; hit below the belt — 1) (спорт.) ударить ниже пояса; 2) нарушать правила, поступать бесчестно, не стесняться в выборе средств; jump the gun—1) (спорт.) начать бежать до выстрела из спортивного пистолета; 2) забежать вперед, предрешать события.*

Phraseological units reflecting historical events and various aspects of the life of the native-speaking people in different periods of the country's history. This group includes:

1) historical events, facts, dates: in Russian: *Мамаево побоище, как швед под Полтавой.*, *snth is rotten in the state of Denmark - подгнило что-то в Датском королевстве (что-то случилось неладное), the last of the Mohicans - последний из могикан (последний представитель); cold war (холодная война'- from the speech of British Prime Minister W. Churchill in Futon 1946; tu house is tu castle (my house is my fortress) - the expression belongs to the English lawyer of the XVII century E. Kok; yellow press (yellow press) since the end of the XIX century attributed to E. To Wardman, the editor of the New York Press magazine, who called the newspapers The World and The New York Journal yellow press, which placed frivolous drawings with humorous text, the main character of which was a child in a yellow shirt; As well be hung (hung) for a sheep as for a lamb - *если тебе суждено быть повешенным за овцу, то почему бы тебе заодно не украсть и ягненка* (an echo of the old English law, according to which stealing a sheep was punishable by death by hanging); the curse of Scotland (map) - *«проклятие Шотландии»* - the nine of diamonds (the map is named so after the similarity with the coat of arms of Earl Dalrymple Stair,*

who caused hatred in Scotland with his pro-English policy).

2) ancient customs, mores, beliefs;; in Russian: *звонить во все колокола, гадать на кофейной гуще*; in English: *have kissed the Blarney stone- быть льстецом (поцеловавший камень в замке Бларни обретает способность льстить, golden handshake - «золотое рукопожатие»-крупное пособие (вручаемое уходящему на пенсию).*

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